

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN: 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**TO DETERMINE THE INCIDENCE OF DIABETIC
NEPHROPATHY AMONG DIABETIC PATIENTS
ATTENDING THE MEDICINE DEPARTMENT OF ALLIED
HOSPITAL FAISALABAD**Dr. Ayesha Iftikhar¹, Dr. Shah Zaib Zahid², Dr. Muhammad Haseeb Farooq Awan³¹ House officer, Allied Hospital, Faisalabad^{2,3} Punjab Medical College Faisalabad**Article Received:** March 2020**Accepted:** April 2020**Published:** May 2020**Abstract:****Aim:** To assess the incidence of diabetic nephropathy in patients attending the Allied Hospital Faisalabad.**Material:** This prospective cross-sectional study has been conducted at the Allied Hospital Faisalabad for one year duration from April 2019 to April 2020. One hundred patients with type 2 diabetes with a duration of diabetes below five years and age 30, 70 years were selected. Urine complete examination and urinary albumin to creatinine ratio was seen in the first void urine.**Results:** In 20% of a hundred patients, urinary albumin index was 30 mg / g and diabetic nephropathy was diagnosed. There was no evidence of diabetic nephropathy in 70% of patients.**Conclusion:** Diabetic patients have a high percentage of diabetic nephropathy in the study.**Key words:** diabetic nephropathy, Urinary albumin creatinine ratio.**Corresponding author:****Dr Ayesha Iftikhar,**

House officer, Allied Hospital, Faisalabad

QR code

Please cite this article in press Ayesha Iftikhar et al, *To Determine The Incidence Of Diabetic Nephropathy Among Diabetic Patients Attending The Medicine Department Of Allied Hospital Faisalabad*, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2020; 07(05).

INTRODUCTION:

Diabetes is an important cause of premature deaths worldwide. It is estimated that by 2025 there will be four hundred and eighteen million people with glucose intolerance and three hundred and eighty million people with type 2 diabetes¹⁻³. About fifty percent of patients with type 2 diabetes will die early. Diabetes often causes complications and costs individuals and society very high. With the appearance of complications, the quality of life decreases⁴⁻⁵. Diabetes is the most common global cause of renal replacement therapy. It is estimated that end-stage renal disease (ESRD) develops in 20% of patients with type 2 diabetes during their lifetime. In the United States, about 40% of recent kidney disease cases are caused by new diabetic nephropathy⁶⁻⁷. Renal impairment develops in many, if not all, patients throughout their lives have renal problems. In the UK diabetes prospective study (UKPDS), 24.9% of patients developed microalbuminuria within ten years of being diagnosed with type 2 diabetes, and 20% of patients with type diabetes achieve ESRD throughout their lives. Impressive evidence suggests that kidney disease can be largely prevented in these patients. In diabetic patients, renal disease is clinically characterized by progress towards diabetic nephropathy and, as a result, by increased urinary albumin excretion with the development of end stage renal disease (ESRD)⁸⁻⁹. The first clinically detectable stage of diabetic nephropathy is microalbuminuria, and low but abnormal (30-299 mg / day) urine albumin is the earliest clinical evidence of nephropathy. This is called microalbuminuria¹⁰.

Without any specific intervention, 80% diabetic with sustained microalbuminuria have 10-20% increase in their rate of urinary albumin excretion per year to the stage of macroalbuminuria or overt nephropathy (urinary albumin excretion ≥ 300 mg per 24hour). The decrease in glomerular filtration rate in macroalbuminuria cases varies considerably from person to person for several years. Due to special intervention, the rate of GFR decline may be delayed. Compared to patients with type 1 diabetes, most people with type 2 diabetes had microalbuminuria and kidney disease shortly after being diagnosed with diabetes. This is because diabetes has been around for many years before the diagnosis is made. Microalbuminuria transforms into macroalbuminuria in 20-40% of patients with type 2 diabetes without specific interventions. Albuminuria is not only the earliest symptom of kidney disease in patients with diabetes, but also a much higher rate of cardiovascular morbidity and mortality. Therefore, microalbuminuria is an indicator of the presence of underlying vascular disease and should aggressively reduce all cardiovascular risk factors. Detection of kidney

disease is very important for preventing and reducing morbidity and mortality from cardiovascular and kidney disease. In a study of more than 1,000 primary care physicians, only 12% detected microalbuminuria in over 50% of patients with type 2 diabetes. The evaluation of microalbuminuria is particularly important in the diagnosis of diabetic nephropathy, because low-level albuminuria, which is negative for bayonet, is a previous clinical manifestation of diabetic nephropathy, which may exist for several years before the development of the filtration index. Interventions should be started when high levels of albumin are detected in the urine to delay the progression of renal disease¹¹. This study shows the percentage of patients suffering from diabetic nephropathy. This study provides us with very important information about kidney disease in diabetics under the age of five.

PATIENTS AND METHODS:

This study is cross-sectional with 100 patients held in the Allied Hospital Faisalabad for one year duration from April 2019 to April 2020. Participants were divided into two groups; without diabetic nephropathy and diabetic nephropathy. Patients with type 2 diabetes aged 30 to 70 years were included, both men and women with diabetes under the age of five. Patients with acute febrile illness (temperature ≥ 100 F) or urinary tract infection (urine with a nitrite positive test strip, over 250 leukocytes per ml) were excluded. During the first visit a full history and physical examination were carried out. Patients who agreed were given a sterile, well-closed plastic container. They received instructions for collecting the first empty urine in the middle of the stream. A pipette and urine microscopic examination were performed. The urine sample was immediately stored at a temperature between 2-4 ° C °. Sodium azide (0.02%) was added to the urine sample to stop bacterial overgrowth. After careful consideration of the exclusion criteria listed above, a urine sample was selected for testing. All samples before the assay were mixed well. For estimation of microalbumin; Randox Microalbumin, an assay based on the principle of Immunoturbidimetric was used. Spectrophotometer was used in laboratory for calculating results. A urine sample was tested for urinary creatinine using the Jaffe reaction.

RESULTS:

The majority of patients, i.e. 37 (37%), are registered at the age of 41-50. There were 48 (48%) women and 52 (52%) men. There were 34 (34%) patients with hypertension and 23 (23%) patients smoked. When calculating the incidence of diabetic nephropathy in 20 (20%) patients with type 2 diabetes lasting less than 5 years, 80 (80%) cases were not reported with these complications (Table 1) Stratification of patients with nephropathy 7

(35%) in the age group of patients for diabetes by age and sex reveals 10 (50%) cases between 51 and 60 years old. The majority of patients were male

(52%). Most patients (70%) with diabetic nephropathy had hypertension. Nine patients with diabetic nephropathy smoked cigarettes (Table 2).

Table 1: Sociodemographic data of the patients

Variable	n.	%age
Age (years)		
≥31-40	26	26
41-50	37	37
51-60	34	34
61-70	3	3
Gender		
Male	52	52
Female	48	48
Hypertensive status		
Hypertensive	34	34
Normotensive	66	66
Smoking habit		
Smoker	23	23
Non-smoker	77	77
Diagnosis		
Diabetic nephropathy	20	20
No evidence of diabetic nephropathy	80	80

Table 2: Stratification of diabetic nephropathy for age and gender

Age (years)	Yes	No
31-40	1(1%)	25(25%)
41-50	7(7%)	30(30%)
51-60	10(10%)	24(24%)
61-70	2(2%)	1(1%)
Gender		
Male	11(11%)	41(41%)
Female	9(9%)	39(39%)

DISCUSSION:

Diabetes has become a serious health problem in Pakistan. Prevalence rates among Pakistani people in rural and urban areas are between 5% and 15%¹¹⁻¹². An ominous development in a person with diabetes is persistent clinical proteinuria (excretion of urinary protein greater than 0.5g/24 h). Ultimately, this leads to a decrease in glomerular filtration rate and ultimately to terminal renal disease or early cardiovascular mortality¹³. In this study, the incidence of diabetic nephropathy was 20%, and the results of this study are comparable to those of other epidemiological studies in which the incidence of diabetic nephropathy was 7 to 53%, i.e.

42% in South Africa, 36.7% in India, Pakistan 13.6% and 9% in the UK population. This change can be attributed to various cases, including assessment method, disease stage and ethnic sensitivity to the development of kidney disease¹⁴. Another finding was the advantage of men with 11 cases in this study compared with 9 women with diabetic nephropathy. The duration of diabetes is an important factor in relation to diabetic nephropathy. In a study in Rawalpindi (a large city in Punjab), 57% of diabetics had diabetic nephropathy, even if the diabetes was less than 10 years old. The highest prevalence of diabetic nephropathy was observed in Korea (56.5%) and the lowest in Pakistan (24.2%).

The American Diabetes Association recommends confirming positive tests due to significant day-to-day variability. Most patients diagnosed with diabetic nephropathy were not aware that diabetes affects their kidneys¹⁵. Therefore, a thorough screening test for diabetic nephropathy is recommended as recommended for the treatment of diabetic kidney disease.

CONCLUSION:

In the light of the results obtained in this small-scale study it is concluded that significant percentage of diabetic patients were found to have evidence of diabetic nephropathy at the time when chronic complications of diabetes are least expected. It is of vital importance to detect diabetic nephropathy earlier so that with appropriate treatment we can reduce morbidity and mortality.

REFERENCES:

1. Abro, Mujeeb, Awn Bin Zafar, Asher Fawwad, Nida Mustafa, Bilal Tahir, Musarrat Riaz, and Abdul Basit. "Prevalence of diabetic micro vascular complications at a tertiary care unit of Karachi, Pakistan." *International Journal of Diabetes in Developing Countries* 39, no. 2 (2019): 325-330.
2. Arambewela, Maulee Hiromi, Noel P. Somasundaram, Hettiarachchige Buddhi Pradeep Ranjan Jayasekara, and Mahesh P. Kumbukage. "Prevalence of Depression and Associated Factors among Patients with Type 2 Diabetes Attending the Diabetic Clinic at a Tertiary Care Hospital in Sri Lanka: A Descriptive Study." *Psychiatry journal* 2019 (2019).
3. Bartaula, Bijay, Manish Subedi, Mayank Mishra Kumar, Monika Shrestha, Navneet Bichha, and Bandana Mudbhari. "Spectrum of complications in chronic kidney disease patients undergoing maintenance hemodialysis: An experience of a tertiary care center in Nepal." *Saudi Journal of Kidney Diseases and Transplantation* 30, no. 1 (2019): 208.
4. Pahuja, Vimal, Pankaj Punjot, Genevieve Fernandes, and Nilesh Chatterjee. "Exploring the factors associated with lipohypertrophy in insulin-treated type 2 diabetes patients in a tertiary care hospital in Mumbai, India." *International Journal of Diabetes in Developing Countries* 39, no. 3 (2019): 426-431.
5. Kantva, Sanvar Mal, and Mahendra Kumar. "RISK FACTORS OF DIABETIC FOOT ULCER AT A TERTIARY CARE HOSPITAL AMONG DIABETIC PATIENTS." *International Journal of Medical and Biomedical Studies* 3, no. 8 (2019).
6. Rahama, Sara, Kamal Mirghani, Mustafa Hussein, and Sami Menasri. "Prevalence of Intensive-care-unit-acquired Thrombocytopenia in a Tertiary Care Hospital in Sudan." *Dr. Sulaiman Al Habib Medical Journal* 1, no. 1 (2019): 12-15.
7. Sirari, T., B. Patro, P. Datta, and P. V. M. Lakshmi. "Levels of compliance of self-care practices of diabetes mellitus type 2 patients: A study from a tertiary care hospital of north india." *International Journal of Diabetes in Developing Countries* 39, no. 1 (2019): 193-200.
8. Khosa, Zulfiqar, Muhammad Zubair Mukhtar Mehboob, and Sania Murad. "HAZARD RATIO PREDICTION| DIABETES MELLITUS AND BMI RELATIONSHIP: STUDY IN A TERTIARY CARE HOSPITAL OF PAKISTAN." *European Journal of Biomedical* 6, no. 10 (2019): 33-38.
9. Jadawji, Chandni, Winston Crasto, Clare Gillies, Debasish Kar, Melanie J. Davies, Kamlesh Khunti, and Samuel Seidu. "Prevalence and progression of diabetic nephropathy in South Asian, white European and African Caribbean people with type 2 diabetes: A systematic review and meta-analysis." *Diabetes, Obesity and Metabolism* 21, no. 3 (2019): 658-673.
10. Toppe, Cecilia, Anna Möllsten, Ingeborg Waernbaum, Staffan Schön, Soffia Gudbjörnsdottir, Mona Landin-Olsson, and Gisela Dahlquist. "Decreasing cumulative incidence of end-stage renal disease in young patients with type 1 diabetes in Sweden: a 38-year prospective nationwide study." *Diabetes care* 42, no. 1 (2019): 27-31.
11. Lou, Jieqiong, Limei Jing, Hui Yang, Fei Qin, Wen Long, and Rong Shi. "Risk factors for diabetic nephropathy complications in community patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus in Shanghai: Logistic regression and classification tree model analysis." *The International journal of health planning and management* 34, no. 3 (2019): 1013-1024.
12. Singh, Harpreet, Atul Saroch, Ashok Kumar Pannu, H. J. Sachin, Navneet Sharma, and Pinaki Dutta. "Clinical and biochemical profile, precipitants and prognostic factors of diabetic ketoacidosis: A retrospective study from a tertiary care center of north India." *Diabetes & Metabolic Syndrome: Clinical Research & Reviews* 13, no. 4 (2019): 2357-2360.
13. Ansaritoroghi, Marzieh, Shankar Prasad Nagaraju, Rajesh Parameshwaran Nair, Vinod Kumar, Lakshman I. Kongwad, Ravindra Prabhu Attur, Girish Menon Ramachandran, and Ajay Hegde. "Study on acute kidney injury in patients with spontaneous intracerebral hemorrhage: an overview from a Tertiary Care Hospital in South India." *World neurosurgery* 123 (2019): e740-e746.

14. Yadav, Baikan Saiteja, Arindam Nandy Roy, and Syeda Sana Fatima. "A cross-sectional study of different rheumatic diseases and their respective comorbidities at a tertiary care hospital in India." *Indian Journal of Rheumatology* 14, no. 1 (2019): 42.
15. Jaiswal, Kavita, Neha Moghe, M. C. Mehta, Kiran Khaladkar, and Lohit Vaishnao. "Knowledge attitude amp practices of type II diabetes mellitus patients in a tertiary care teaching institute of central India." *Journal of Diabetes, Metabolic Disorders & Control* 6, no. 6 (2019).